

Comparative Relationship Between ... (Datti, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045125>

Comparative Relationship Between Entry Qualification and Academic Performance among Colleges of Education Students in North-West, Nigeria

Datti, Shehu Mohammed
dattishehu@gmail.com
Tel; 08037903724/ 07040048292

Department of Mathematics, Kaduna State College of Education, Gidan Waya, Kafanchan, Kaduna State

Abstract

This study investigated the Comparative Relationship between Entry Qualification and Academic Performance among Colleges of Education Students in North-West, Nigeria. ie the population of the study consists of all colleges of education final year Mathematics/Sciences and Technical education students in Northwest Nigeria. A sample of 138 students were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. Ex-post factor design was adopted and the data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation). Pearson product moment correlation coefficient, multiple regressions and analysis of variance. The finding revealed that the two entry modes (UTME and DE) have linear positive relationship with the final CGPA, the Direct Entry (DE) mode of admission is the best predictor and contributor to the student's academic performance. Thus, the best performance in the final CGPA in Mathematics and Sciences. Based on the findings, it was recommended that more emphasis should be given to the DE entry mode in admitting candidates into Mathematics and Science Education programme in the Colleges in a bid to raise the standard of Mathematics and Science Performance,

Keyword: Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination, DE- Direct Entry, National Certificate in Education. And Cumulative Grade Points Average

Introduction

Science and Mathematics Education occupies a key position in the Nigerian educational system, reflecting the significant roles of mathematics in the contemporary society, a 'credit' (c) pass at O/level examination is a pre-requisite for admission into science and technology-based courses in every institution of higher learning. But students' performance in mathematics at various stages of the educational system is very disappointing. Academic performance has been described as the scholastic Standing of a student at given moment. This scholastic Standing could be explained in terms of the grades obtained in a course or groups of Courses. Mallory, 2004, argued that Performance is a measure of output and that the main output in education are expressed, in terms of skills, attitude of individual as a result of their experience within the school settings. Academic performances is regarded as Student's performance in an examination as being depended on his cumulative grades point average (Jansen 2004) detained academic performance. As the process of developing the capabilities and potentials of individual student so as to prepare that individual to be successful in a specific society or Culture, Candidates' admission or placement into Nigerian institutions of higher learning irrespective of whether the institution is federal, state or private owned in contingent on meeting a prescribed cut off marks.

In the 1960s very few Candidates were seeking for admission into higher institutions and those who were admitted got it through hard work. Any Candidate/student who found himself/herself those admitted was therefore considered. Intelligent and academically superior to his/her peers (Erigha, 2001). Over the years, the number of Students applying to enter higher institutions in Nigeria has been on the increase. However, just a fraction of these applicants are admitted each year. Admission into higher institutions in Nigeria is very Competitive due to high number of Students vying for the limited slots available. It is thus expected that only the best will be admitted since academic merit is the major criterial used for admission. Initially, each institution handled its admission process autonomously. As such there was variance in the Criteria used since each institution adopted what it considered most appropriate for it. However, over time, the need to harmonize admission processes across the country was realized. As a result of that the Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) was established to coordinate and standardize tertiary institutions processes in the County. Each Course and or institution was given a Cut-off mark which varied from one institution to another. Meeting the prescribed cut-off mark for a course in a particular institution thus qualified a candidate to be provisionally admitted. However, admissions were confirmed on the Candidate obtaining good grades in his/her O/level Subjects at the end of their Secondary School education. The cut-off mark/points for any mode or criteria of

Comparative Relationship Between ... (Datti, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045125>

admission, the candidates are required to undergo screening examination as a condition for admission into the required programmed. This is because of the following reasons:

These institutions do not have confidence in the various certificates and entry points Possessed by the candidates. Selection for admission is highly competitive because of the large number of candidates seeking for admission. Institutions are looking for an objective means of screening Candidates that those admitted are on the assumption that they have very high chance of Success at the end of their studies (Asaolu, 2003). Hence, the eventual graduates would be qualitative, self-reliant, functional and skillful mathematics and science educators that would transform mathematics teaching and learning in schools for better output. The focus of this research study is on the Predictive validity of different entry mode in the performance of NCE Students in Mathematics, Science and Technical Education.

Statement of the Research Problem

Academic success is no doubt the main focus of all educational activities. The ultimate goal of every tertiary institution is quality product of competent graduate who would function effectively in the larger society. But the decay in the Nigeria educational system calls for attention. The research for the most desirable and most acceptable model of selecting candidate for admission into Nigeria tertiary institution continues (Asaolu, 2003). This is evidenced by public opinion about the standard of students graduating from Nigeria college of Education with NCE certificates. The problem of this research, therefore, is to determine how significantly Students entry qualification into National Certificate in Education (NCE) in mathematics, technical and science education could predict their final performance at these three colleges of education: Kaduna State college of education, gidan-waya: federal college of education (technical) Gusau, Zamfara state and Federal College of Education, Zaria. There are minimum entry requirements that Candidates must possess before they can be admitted into NCE Programmed in the colleges of education. The requirement must be met for both UTME and Direct entry Candidates. Candidate are expected to possess NECO/WAEC, SSCE, and NAPTECH or its equivalents with credits in five (5) Subjects (including Mathematics and English) relevant to their course (s) at not more than two (2) sittings. It is hope and assumed that all those admitted will be able to cope with the academic rigouts but contrary to this expectation, some drop out on the way without graduating, some change their courses and others spend extra year (s) before graduating while some graduate with a low grade, just Pass. This Scenario Show's that performance may be a function of the mode of entry qualification.

Objectives of the Study

Specifically, this research seeks to;

1. Examine the mean academic performance of graduating mathematics students who are admitted into higher institutions through the two (2) modes of admission criteria.
2. Find out the difference between mode of entry and academic achievement of NCE students.
3. Compare the academic performance of students admitted through direct entry and UTME.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were generated and tested at 0.05 level of significance in this study.

1. H_{01} There is no significant relationship between UTME scores and final academic performance of student in NCE of Science and Mathematics Education of Colleges of Education in the Northwest Zone.
2. H_{02} There is no significant relationship between Direct Entry (DE) points and final academic performance in NCE Science and Mathematics Education of Colleges of Education in the Northwest Zone.
3. H_{03} There is no significant relationship between the mean scores of the final academic performance of graduate in NCE Science and Mathematics Education of Colleges of Education in the Northwest Zone.
4. None of the entry mode of UTME and DE entry points will best predict student' final performance in NCE Science and Mathematics Education of Colleges of Education in the Northwest Zone

Methodology

An ex-post factor design was adopted in this research. The population of the study consists of all colleges of education final year Mathematics/Sciences and Technical education students in Northwest Nigeria. A sample of 138 students were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique In carrying out this

Comparative Relationship Between ... (Datti, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045125>

research, two instruments were employed; namely: Inventory and students academic results from the schools. The inventory is to take care of the list of students in the intact class/level to be used as sample, while the results revealed academic achievement. The research instrument was divided into two major sections: Section A contained items that sought information on the inventory (that is, gender, mode of entry and students level). Section B of the instrument contained the result of the students. The method of data collection adopted in this study involved the gathering of information and data through both primary and secondary sources. The primary data was gathered from the inventory / intact class, and the secondary data was derived from Students Result. Data obtained was analyzed using descriptive statistics for the participants' bio-data and various analysis tools like (t-test, Chi-square, and Anova) were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significance relationship between students' UTME scores and their final academic performance in Mathematics and science education.

In testing this hypothesis, data on 137 selected UTME candidates was collected and analyzed. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was calculated using SPSS 17.0 version for Windows Computer Software. The Pearson product moment correlation coefficient index was presented in the Table 1.

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient for Students' UTME Scores and their Final Academic performance (CGPA).

		UTME Score	CGPA
UTME Scores	Person correlation		0.239
	Sig. (2-tailed)	1	0.005
	N		138
CGPA		138	
	Pearson correlation	0.239	1
	Sig (2-tailed)	0.005	
		138	138

Source: data from the three colleges

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 1. is the summary of the degree of relationship between UTME scores and final academic performance (CGPA), the table showed a correlation coefficient of 0.239 between students' UTME scores and academic performance (i.e CGPA) which was significantly higher than critical table value of 0.178 at 0.05level of significant and 137 degrees of freedom. Therefore the correlation coefficient was significant at 0.01level of significance. Therefore, since p-value was less than level of significant (i.e. $p < 0.01$), the hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was statistically significant relationship between students' UTME scores and final academic performance in in Mathematics and science education of colleges of Education and the North West.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between students' Direct Entry points and their final academic performance in NCE Science Education and Mathematics.

In testing this hypothesis, data on 61 selected DE candidates was collected and analyzed. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was computed using SPSS 17.0 version for Windows Computer Software and the results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient for Students 'DE Points and their Final Academic Performance'(CGPA)

		DE points	CGPA
DE Point	Pearson correlation	1	0.551
	Sig (2 tailed)	61	61
CGPA	Pearson correlation	0.551	1

Comparative Relationship Between ... (Datti, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045125>

Sig (2-tailed)	0.000	61
N	61	

Source: data from the three colleges

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 2. is the summary of the degree of relationship between the variables (students' DE points and their final academic performance) in NCE of Science Education and Mathematics at College of Education and Northwest. The table showed a correlation index of 0.551 which is considerably higher than the critical table value of 0.250 at 0.05 level of significance and 60 degrees of freedom, thus the correlation is statistically significant at 0.000 levels. Therefore, the null hypothesis 2 was also rejected.

Hypothesis: 3 there is no significant difference in the means scores of the final academic performance of graduates of NCE in Mathematics and science admitted through UTME and DE entry modes.

In testing this hypothesis, the final academic performance i.e CGPA of the sampled subjects was collected and used. Although the UTME and DE and were measured by different scales, the researcher converted each of the two variables into an interval scale. Descriptive statistics, Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Post Hoc test (scheffe's test) were computed electronically using SPSS version 17.0 for windows computer software to find out whether there is a significant difference in the final academic performance of students admitted through UTME and DE and where the difference exist. The results are shown below in the tables 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 3: Mean Scores and Standard Deviations for Students' Final Academic Performance (CGPA)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
UTME	138	1.9950	0.63814	0.05413
DI:	61	3.1713	0.49674	0.07596
Total	199	2.2920	0.71529	0.04267

Source: data from the three colleges

Table 3. Is a summary of the mean scores and standard deviations of students' final academic performance in the NCE of Science Education and Mathematics. The result indicated that the Direct Entry mode had the highest mean of 3.1713. While the Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) has a mean of 1.9950. On the other hand the UTME mode has the highest standard deviation of 0.63814 followed by the Direct Entry with 0.49674 modes. This is an indication that the least performance was from UTME candidates

Table 4: Analysis of Variance for Significant Difference in the Mean Scores of Final Academic Performance of Students Admitted Through UTME and DE.

Variance	SS	Df	MS	F-Cal	F-Crit	Sig
Between Groups	29.673	2	14.836	36.312	3.04	0.000
Within Groups	113.585	278	0.4090			

Source: data from the three colleges

Table 4. is a summary of analysis of variance for significant difference in the final academic performance in terms of CGPA of graduates of Mathematics and Science Education admitted through the two modes and (UTME). The result indicated that the calculated value of F is 36.312 (i.e. Fcal=36.312) which is significantly greater than the critical table value of F which is 3.04 (i.e Fcrit=3.04) at 2 and 0.05 level of significance and at a p-value of 0.000. Since calculated value of F is greater than the critical table value of F (i.e Fcal>Fcri) and p<0.05 the null hypothesis 4 which states that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of the final academic performance of students admitted through the two mode was rejected. This implies that, there was significant difference in the final academic performance of students admitted into NCE in Mathematics and Science at the said Colleges of Education. Since the result of table 3 showed that the null hypothesis was rejected, it means that at least one of the means isn't the same as the other means.

Comparative Relationship Between ... (Datti, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045125>

The result was further subjected to a Scheffe' test to figure out where the differences lie and the result of the test is shown in Table 5 below:

Table 5: Scheffe's test for Significant Difference in the Mean Scores of Final Academic Performance of Students Admitted through UTME and DE.

Level	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05 (i.e a = 0.05)		
		1	2	3
UTME	138	1.9950		
DE	61		2.8014	
Sig	1.000	1.000	1.000	

Source: data from the three colleges

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size=83.974.

b. The group sizes are unequal

Table 5. is a summary of Scheffe's Post Hoc test for significant difference in the means of students' final academic performance in NCE of Science Education and Mathematics. The result revealed that UTME had 1.9950, and Direct Entry had 2.8014 which indicated that there was statistically significant difference in the final academic performance of student in favor of the Direct Entry.

Discussion of Findings

The aim of this research work was to determine the predictive validity of entry qualifications on final academic performance of NCE Science Education and Mathematics at the colleges of Education. The study correlated students' entry points and their corresponding final academic performance in Mathematics and Science Education programme on one hand and on the other hand determined the predictive validity of the entry qualifications and significant difference in the mean scores of final academic performances of students admitted through the two modes.

The results of the findings indicated that there was positive and linear correlation between each entry points and their final academic performance in Mathematics and Science Education in the colleges of education although with different degree of strength. This is in line with the previous similar studies by Durotoluwa (2000) who found a positive correlation between entry grades at JSS and academic performance at high level (SSS) of educational pursuit. It is also in line with the findings of Awaisu (2002) who found that there was high positive relationship between entry qualification and academic performance of students in Biology at Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel. It is also in line with the findings of Kolawale and Ilugbosi (2007) in Ekiti who found that there was a significant positive and linear relationship between basic cognitive entry grades and final cumulative grade point average of students in Mathematics. Thus, cognitive grades contributed significantly to the overall CGPA of the selected students in mathematics and Science in NCE.

The result is also in line with the findings of Ali (2008) in Pakistan who found that there is strong positive relationship between admission criteria (entry scores) and subsequent academic performance of students in Diploma in General Nursing at Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan. Similarly, the result also coincidences with the findings of Adeyemi (2010) found that there was positive correlation between entry grade point of credit in Mathematics and academic performance of Educational Management students in the universities in Ondo and Ekiti states.

The result also shows that the Direct Entry mode was the best predictor of academic performance in NCE in Mathematics and Science Education. This coincides with the findings of Njoku (2002) who found that the DE entry points slightly predicted academic performance only in the faculty of education and extension services in UDUS. This perhaps could be due to their previous A-level training in Colleges of Education and Polytechnics, accumulated experience and the result also shows that the Direct Entry mode was the best predictor of academic performance in NCE in Mathematics and Science Education.

On the other hand, this finding contradicts the findings of Adeyemi (2009) who found that the Direct Entry mode was the worst predictor of success in the university degree at Ondo and Ekiti states. The results also indicated

Comparative Relationship Between ... (Datti, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045125>

that the UTME entry mode was the least predictor of academic performance and do not relate well with academic performance. This finding agrees with the findings of Oyebola (2004) who found that the UTME scores do not relate well with academic performance of students in Medical School.

Similarly, Obioma and Salau (2007) who found that the UTME scores alone was the least predictor variable of student's final year CGPA in Nigerian universities. It is also consistent with the findings of Ojirinde and Kolo (2009) who found that some relationships exist between scores in Universities Matriculation Examination (UTME) and corresponding academic performance in terms of final cumulative grade points average (CGPA) especially when it is with SSCE result. On the other hand, the result contradicted the findings of Njoku (2002) who found a negative correlation between UTME scores and final university result at Usman Danfodio University, Sokoto.

The results also revealed that there was significant difference in the final academic performance of students admitted through the two modes in favor of the Direct Entry. This contradicts the findings of Dahiru (2010) who found that there was no significant difference in the academic achievement of Direct Entry and Non-Direct Entry students in FCE Katsina. The results also disagree with the findings of Moses & Solomon (2002) who found that there was no significant difference in the final academic performance of Pre-NCE and JAMB students in FCE Pankshin.

The value of the multiple regression $R = 0.614, 0.653$ and 0.851 in table 4 showed that there was a significant linear and positive relationship between students' entry qualification and final cumulative grade point average (CGPA) of 2.50 and above (Merit and above) in NCE of Science Education and Mathematics. These findings corroborated previous and similar researches by Adegboye (1997), Adeyemi (2009), and Kolawole and Illugbusi (2007) who found in their studies that there was a significant positive and linear relationship between students' entry qualifications and their final academic performance in the Universities. On the other hand, this finding is inconsistent with the findings of Momoh-Olle (1998) and Kolawole, Oginni & Fayomi (2011) who found no significant relationship between entry grades and academic performance in the university.

This showed that the entry points have significant contribution to the final cumulative grade point average of the selected candidates in NCE Science Education and Mathematics in these colleges of Education. These finding is consistent with the findings of Alias and Ahmad (2006), Ajuonuma and Mkpa (2009), Adeyemi (2010) and Ajayi, Lawani Muraina (2011) respectively who found in their studies that entry grades/points contributed significantly to the final year academic performance in terms CGPA of students in tertiary institutions.

Conclusion

The DE candidates performed significantly better than UTME. The UTME scores are the worse predictor of final academic performance in NCE of Science Education and Mathematics. There were few Direct Entry applicants in general as such only very few were admitted into Mathematics and Science Education, hence there were few numbers of admitted Direct Entry candidates. There was statistically significant difference in the final academic performance of UTME and DE and candidates in NCE Science Education and Mathematics in favor of DE candidates.

Recommendations

1. Based on the findings of this research study the following recommendations were made: The examination bodies such JAMB, WAEC, NECO, NABTEB etc, should continue to improve the quality of the development and administration of their examinations.
2. Government should endeavor to recruit more specialist teachers in mathematics so that more emphasis could be given to the teaching of Mathematics in secondary schools.
3. Since the UTME was designed as a screening examination, the items on it should include both achievement and aptitude testing items. Thus, in designing the aptitude test, Mathematics Educators involved should consult and involve expert in test, Measurement and evaluation, so that the psychometric properties of the aptitude test can be ascertained and ensured to avoid capricious item selected.
4. There is also the need for a national policy document to strengthen the post-UTME screening examination by using uniform guidelines as well as valid and reliable instruments and mandatory inclusion of experts in Test, Measurement and Evaluation in the Post-UTME Screening Committee.

Comparative Relationship Between ... (Datti, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15045125>

Acknowledgement

I wish to express my profound gratitude to the following people Dr Labaran Magashi, Dr Abdulraham Zubairu, Dr Mallam Abubakar Abba, Zaidu S Datti and all those that assisted in one way or the other for the successful completion of this research work, may Allah bless you all.

References

- Ali (2012) Predictive validity of a uniform Entrance Test for the health professional,
- Adeyemi, T.O (2009). Mode Od Study as A Predictor Of Success In Final Year Bacherlor Of Education Degree Examination In The University In Ekiti And Ondo State, Nigeria. Middle – East Journal Of Scientific Research, 4(1), 10-19.
- Adeyemi, T.o (2010). Credit in mathematics in senior secondary certificate examination as a predictor of success in educational management in universities in ekiti and ondo state. Research journal of mathematics and statistics, 2(1), 14-22.
- Asalu, A.G. (2003). Predictive Validity of JSC Mathematics Examination on the Performance of Students in Science subjects in Ekiti State Secondary Schools. An unpublished M.Ed. thesis, Faculty of Education, University of Ado-Ekiti.
- Awaisu, N.S. (2002), Entry Qualifications as Predictors of Students' Academic Performance in Biology. A case study of Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel. An unpublished M.Ed dissertation, Faculty of Education and Extension Services, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.
- .Dahiru SY. (2010). Comparative Study on Academic Performance of Direct Entry and Non-Direct Entry Nigeria Certificate in Education students. Journal of Escational Research and Development. 51(1). 89-94.
- Durotoluwa, J.O. (2000). Predictive Validity of JSS Certificate in Mathematics: A case study of Owo Local Government Area, Educational Thought, Journal of Faculty of Education. Ondo State University, Akugba-Akoko, 1(1), 30-34.
- Erigha A (2001). Educated prostitutes. Sunday Tribune of 21 January
- Kolawale, E.B. & Ilugbusi, A.A. (2007), Cognitive Entry Grade as Predictors of Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics in Nigerian Universities Medwell Journal, 2(3), 322-326.
- Kolawole. E.B., Oginni, LO. & Fayomi, O.E. (2011). Ordinary Level Results as Predictors of Students' Academic Performance in Chemistry in Nigerian Universities. Journal of Educational Research and reviews, 6(16), 889-892.
- Momoh Olle, (1998). The Relationship Between Student's Entry Grades and Academic Achievement at Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin Gusau Journal of Education, 2(1), 169-179
- Njoku, J.N (2002). Student Scores in UTME As Predictors of Academic Performance Of Student Of Usman Danfodio University. An Unpublished M. Ed Dissertation, Faculty of Education and Extension Services, Usman Danfodio University, Sokoto.
- Ojerinde. D. and Kolo, T.N. (2009). Prediction of First Year University Education Performance form entry Academic Performances: Presented at the 27th Annual.
- Obioma, G. & Salau, M. (2007). Predictive Validity of Public Examinations. A Case Study of Nigeria. Paper Presented at the 33rd Annual Conference of International Association for Educational Assessment (IAEA) held in Bäku, Azerbaijan, 16-21 September, 2007.
- Moses, O.A. & Solomon, E.M. (2002). Entry Qualifications as Determinants of Final Performance. Gusau journal of Education, 6(1), 59-64
- Oyebola. D. D. O. (2004). The importance of O-level Grades in Medical School Proceedings of the Physiological September 16-17 at Abraka, Nigeria, Pp: 13 Plat Turocy and McGlumphy (2001). The Predictive Validity of Preadmission. Criteria, Scholastic Aptitude Test Scores and High School Grade Point Average on College Grade Point Average of Graduates of Atheletic Training lines at Rangos school of Programme and five other Allied Health Disciplines health sciences, Duquesne University Pittsburgh, USA. Journal of Medical Sciences, 8(1), 102-108.